

TABLE S1. List of sampled material. Provided as a separate file.

TABLE S2. Results of PCA.

A. Total dataset (i.e., 7 limb variables)

	<i>PC1</i>	<i>PC2</i>	<i>PC3</i>	<i>PC4</i>	<i>PC5</i>	<i>PC6</i>	<i>PC7</i>
Proportion of Variance	0.503	0.223	0.110	0.092	0.044	0.028	0.000
Cumulative Proportion	0.503	0.726	0.837	0.928	0.972	1.000	1.000
Loadings							
<i>Humerus</i>	-0.472	0.221	-0.226	0.147	-0.163	0.623	-0.491
<i>Radioulna</i>	-0.433	0.372	-0.070	0.080	0.245	-0.702	-0.331
<i>Femur</i>	0.363	-0.216	-0.727	0.043	-0.375	-0.253	-0.295
<i>Tibiofibula</i>	0.493	-0.034	0.081	0.033	0.659	0.157	-0.537
<i>Proximal Tarsals</i>	0.335	0.440	0.456	-0.291	-0.529	-0.075	-0.340
<i>Metacarpal arch</i>	-0.282	-0.415	-0.009	-0.837	0.066	-0.019	-0.209
<i>Metatarsal arch</i>	-0.153	-0.631	0.448	0.430	-0.233	-0.158	-0.337

B. Reduced dataset (i.e., 5 limb variables)

	<i>PC1</i>	<i>PC2</i>	<i>PC3</i>	<i>PC4</i>	<i>PC5</i>
Proportion of Variance	0.648	0.238	0.074	0.040	0.000
Cumulative Proportion	0.648	0.886	0.960	1.000	1.000
Loadings					
<i>Humerus</i>	-0.528	0.119	-0.110	-0.610	0.568
<i>Radioulna</i>	-0.518	-0.098	0.130	0.753	0.372
<i>Femur</i>	0.332	0.666	-0.528	0.243	0.328
<i>Tibiofibula</i>	0.510	0.002	0.652	-0.038	0.559
<i>Proximal Tarsals</i>	0.288	-0.730	-0.516	0.022	0.344

TABLE S3. Results of phylogenetic MANOVA and pairwise comparisons.

	Total dataset			Reduced dataset		
	F	Z	P-value	F	Z	P-value
	36.013	7.6975	0.0001	46.086	7.5403	0.0001
Pairwise comparisons						
J:Sw		1.544646	0.0628		1.024559	0.1506
J:WH		7.383121	0.0001		7.021309	0.0001
Sw:WH		3.609363	0.0002		3.7508	0.0001

TABLE S4. Classification of fossils by pFDA using the total set of variables. Species for which the predicted LM varies under different lambda values marked with “*”.

Species	Optimal lambda (0.13)				Optimal lambda + 0.02				Optimal lambda - 0.02			
	LM	P(J)	P(Sw)	P(WH)	LM	P(J)	P(Sw)	P(WH)	LM	P(J)	P(Sw)	P(WH)
<i>Prosalirus bitis</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Notobatrachus degiustoi</i>	WH	0.000	0.001	0.999	WH	0.000	0.001	0.998	WH	0.000	0.000	1.000
<i>Vieraella herbstii*</i>	Sw	0.365	0.541	0.093	Sw	0.295	0.632	0.073	J	0.449	0.430	0.120
<i>Eodiscoglossus santonjae</i>	Sw	0.224	0.612	0.164	Sw	0.209	0.633	0.158	Sw	0.243	0.584	0.173
<i>Wealdenbatrachus jucarensis</i>	J	0.984	0.014	0.002	J	0.981	0.016	0.002	J	0.986	0.012	0.002
<i>Wealdenbatrachus sp</i>	J	0.991	0.009	0.000	J	0.988	0.011	0.000	J	0.994	0.006	0.000
<i>Hyogobatrachus wadai</i>	J	0.961	0.005	0.034	J	0.954	0.008	0.038	J	0.966	0.004	0.030
<i>Iberobatrachus angelae</i>	J	0.975	0.022	0.003	J	0.972	0.024	0.004	J	0.978	0.019	0.002
<i>MCCM-LH11392</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Genibatrachus baoshanensis</i>	J	0.966	0.014	0.021	J	0.959	0.017	0.023	J	0.972	0.010	0.018
<i>Rhadinosteus parvus</i>	J	0.939	0.040	0.021	J	0.924	0.052	0.024	J	0.952	0.029	0.018
<i>Neusibatrachus wilferti</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Gracilibatrachus avallei</i>	Sw	0.229	0.763	0.007	Sw	0.224	0.767	0.008	Sw	0.235	0.758	0.007
<i>Palaeobatrachus sp</i>	Sw	0.340	0.545	0.116	Sw	0.336	0.541	0.122	Sw	0.344	0.546	0.110
<i>Paleobatrachus tobieni</i>	J	0.880	0.090	0.030	J	0.864	0.103	0.033	J	0.898	0.076	0.026
<i>Palaeobatrachus goldfussi</i>	J	0.484	0.339	0.176	J	0.469	0.349	0.181	J	0.503	0.326	0.172
<i>Palaeobatrachus grandipes</i>	Sw	0.061	0.848	0.092	Sw	0.061	0.844	0.095	Sw	0.060	0.851	0.089
<i>Cordicephalus gracilis</i>	Sw	0.060	0.836	0.105	Sw	0.064	0.820	0.116	Sw	0.055	0.851	0.094
<i>Crato pipimorph</i>	Sw	0.196	0.791	0.013	Sw	0.222	0.761	0.017	Sw	0.169	0.821	0.010
<i>Cratopipa novaolindensis</i>	Sw	0.024	0.965	0.012	Sw	0.029	0.955	0.016	Sw	0.018	0.973	0.009
<i>Eoxenopoides reuningi</i>	Sw	0.060	0.870	0.070	Sw	0.074	0.836	0.089	Sw	0.046	0.902	0.052
<i>UnGAA01</i>	WH	0.010	0.371	0.619	WH	0.012	0.346	0.642	WH	0.008	0.402	0.589
<i>Saltenia ibanezi</i>	Sw	0.388	0.596	0.016	Sw	0.439	0.541	0.020	Sw	0.331	0.658	0.012
<i>Vulcanobatrachus mandelai</i>	Sw	0.369	0.607	0.025	Sw	0.407	0.563	0.030	Sw	0.324	0.656	0.019
<i>Shelania pascuali</i>	Sw	0.015	0.908	0.077	Sw	0.018	0.890	0.092	Sw	0.012	0.927	0.062
<i>Llankibatrachus truebae*</i>	Sw	0.009	0.522	0.469	WH	0.010	0.487	0.503	Sw	0.007	0.566	0.426
<i>Xenopus arabiensis</i>	J	0.664	0.279	0.057	J	0.686	0.249	0.066	J	0.634	0.318	0.048
<i>Eorubeta nevadensis</i>	WH	0.271	0.305	0.423	WH	0.273	0.305	0.422	WH	0.270	0.304	0.426
<i>Prospea holoserisca*</i>	WH	0.464	0.053	0.483	J	0.484	0.064	0.452	WH	0.440	0.042	0.518
<i>Aerugoamnis paulus</i>	J	0.819	0.159	0.022	J	0.801	0.176	0.024	J	0.839	0.141	0.020
<i>Miopelodytes gilmorei</i>	J	0.486	0.067	0.447	J	0.479	0.075	0.446	J	0.492	0.059	0.450
<i>Sanshuibatrachus sinensis</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Macropelobates linguensis</i>	WH	0.197	0.128	0.676	WH	0.207	0.130	0.663	WH	0.185	0.123	0.692
<i>Pelobates decheni</i>	WH	0.222	0.338	0.440	WH	0.231	0.340	0.429	WH	0.214	0.333	0.454
<i>Pelobates cf decheni</i>	J	0.509	0.065	0.426	J	0.515	0.073	0.413	J	0.502	0.056	0.442
<i>Eopelobates deani</i>	J	0.751	0.203	0.046	J	0.733	0.220	0.047	J	0.771	0.185	0.044
<i>Eopelobates anthracinus</i>	WH	0.338	0.155	0.507	WH	0.334	0.171	0.495	WH	0.341	0.137	0.523
<i>Eopelobates bayeri</i>	J	0.876	0.035	0.089	J	0.866	0.042	0.092	J	0.886	0.029	0.086
<i>Indobatrachus pusillus</i>	Sw	0.195	0.462	0.344	Sw	0.198	0.459	0.344	Sw	0.192	0.462	0.345
<i>Cratia gracilis</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Eurycephalella alcinae</i>	J	0.908	0.009	0.084	J	0.902	0.010	0.087	J	0.913	0.007	0.080
<i>Calypptocephalella canqueli</i>	WH	0.051	0.181	0.768	WH	0.056	0.188	0.756	WH	0.047	0.171	0.782
<i>Arariphrynus placidoi</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Estesiella boliviensis</i>	WH	0.190	0.305	0.505	WH	0.186	0.331	0.483	WH	0.195	0.275	0.530
<i>Liaobatrachus grabaui</i>	J	0.790	0.008	0.202	J	0.780	0.011	0.209	J	0.800	0.006	0.194
<i>Liaobatrachus zhaoi</i>	WH	0.178	0.020	0.802	WH	0.183	0.026	0.791	WH	0.173	0.014	0.813

<i>Liaobatrachus beiopiaoensis</i>	WH	0.158	0.046	0.796		WH	0.161	0.061	0.778		WH	0.154	0.032	0.814
<i>Liaobatrachus macilentus</i>	Sw	0.103	0.778	0.119		Sw	0.095	0.793	0.112		Sw	0.112	0.758	0.129

TABLE S5. Classification of fossils by pFDA using the reduced set of variables. For all species, the inferred LM remains unchanged across the different lambda values.

Species	Optimal lambda (0.13)				Optimal lambda + 0.02				Optimal lambda - 0.02			
	LM	P(J)	P(Sw)	P(WH)	LM	P(J)	P(Sw)	P(WH)	LM	P(J)	P(Sw)	P(WH)
<i>Prosalirus bitis</i>	Sw	0.007	0.903	0.091	Sw	0.007	0.918	0.076	Sw	0.007	0.883	0.110
<i>Notobatrachus degiustoi</i>	WH	0.000	0.039	0.961	WH	0.000	0.058	0.942	WH	0.000	0.025	0.975
<i>Vieraella herbstii</i>	Sw	0.004	0.993	0.003	Sw	0.004	0.993	0.003	Sw	0.004	0.992	0.004
<i>Eodiscoglossus santonjae</i>	Sw	0.096	0.847	0.057	Sw	0.100	0.840	0.061	Sw	0.093	0.853	0.053
<i>Wealdenbatrachus jucarensis</i>	J	0.988	0.011	0.001	J	0.987	0.012	0.002	J	0.989	0.010	0.001
<i>Wealdenbatrachus sp</i>	J	0.655	0.343	0.002	J	0.651	0.347	0.002	J	0.659	0.339	0.001
<i>Hyogobatrachus wadai</i>	Sw	0.341	0.567	0.091	Sw	0.342	0.561	0.096	Sw	0.340	0.574	0.086
<i>Iberobatrachus angelae</i>	J	0.882	0.105	0.012	J	0.882	0.104	0.014	J	0.882	0.107	0.011
<i>MCCM-LH11392</i>	Sw	0.392	0.503	0.106	Sw	0.383	0.509	0.108	Sw	0.402	0.494	0.103
<i>Genibatrachus baoshanensis</i>	J	0.680	0.271	0.049	J	0.672	0.275	0.053	J	0.688	0.267	0.045
<i>Rhadinosteus parvus</i>	Sw	0.151	0.840	0.008	Sw	0.158	0.832	0.009	Sw	0.144	0.849	0.007
<i>Neusibatrachus wilferti</i>	Sw	0.087	0.889	0.024	Sw	0.090	0.884	0.026	Sw	0.085	0.893	0.022
<i>Gracilibatrachus avallei</i>	Sw	0.019	0.977	0.004	Sw	0.021	0.975	0.005	Sw	0.017	0.979	0.004
<i>Palaebatrachus sp</i>	Sw	0.077	0.555	0.368	Sw	0.079	0.553	0.368	Sw	0.075	0.555	0.370
<i>Paleobatrachus tobieni</i>	J	0.471	0.283	0.246	J	0.462	0.290	0.248	J	0.481	0.274	0.245
<i>Palaebatrachus goldfussi</i>	WH	0.134	0.388	0.478	WH	0.135	0.394	0.471	WH	0.133	0.380	0.487
<i>Palaebatrachus grandipes</i>	Sw	0.025	0.712	0.262	Sw	0.027	0.709	0.264	Sw	0.024	0.714	0.262
<i>Cordicephalus gracilis</i>	Sw	0.043	0.496	0.461	Sw	0.046	0.492	0.462	Sw	0.041	0.499	0.460
<i>Crato pipimorph</i>	J	0.560	0.324	0.116	J	0.565	0.310	0.125	J	0.553	0.339	0.107
<i>Cratopipa novaolindensis</i>	J	0.373	0.263	0.364	J	0.374	0.256	0.370	J	0.372	0.271	0.357
<i>Eoxenopoides reuningi</i>	Sw	0.205	0.496	0.299	Sw	0.210	0.474	0.316	Sw	0.198	0.521	0.281
<i>UnGAA01</i>	WH	0.086	0.201	0.713	WH	0.089	0.195	0.716	WH	0.084	0.208	0.709
<i>Saltenia ibanezi</i>	J	0.634	0.297	0.068	J	0.637	0.289	0.075	J	0.631	0.307	0.062
<i>Vulcanobatrachus mandelai</i>	Sw	0.310	0.575	0.115	Sw	0.320	0.556	0.124	Sw	0.300	0.596	0.105
<i>Shelania pascuali</i>	Sw	0.044	0.853	0.103	Sw	0.048	0.838	0.113	Sw	0.040	0.868	0.092
<i>Llankibatrachus truebae</i>	WH	0.117	0.224	0.659	WH	0.116	0.225	0.660	WH	0.118	0.224	0.658
<i>Xenopus arabiensis</i>	WH	0.304	0.158	0.538	WH	0.299	0.156	0.545	WH	0.311	0.160	0.530
<i>Eorubeta nevadensis</i>	J	0.494	0.183	0.322	J	0.490	0.182	0.328	J	0.498	0.185	0.317
<i>Prospea holoserisca</i>	Sw	0.335	0.421	0.244	Sw	0.342	0.422	0.236	Sw	0.327	0.418	0.255
<i>Aerugoamnis paulus</i>	Sw	0.475	0.491	0.034	Sw	0.478	0.485	0.037	Sw	0.471	0.498	0.032
<i>Miopelodytes gilmorei</i>	WH	0.268	0.220	0.512	WH	0.267	0.221	0.512	WH	0.270	0.217	0.514
<i>Sanshuibatrachus sinensis</i>	J	0.606	0.371	0.022	J	0.607	0.369	0.024	J	0.606	0.373	0.021
<i>Macropelobates linguensis</i>	WH	0.029	0.107	0.865	WH	0.031	0.109	0.859	WH	0.026	0.104	0.871
<i>Pelobates decheni</i>	WH	0.252	0.333	0.414	WH	0.263	0.324	0.412	WH	0.240	0.343	0.417
<i>Pelobates cf decheni</i>	WH	0.267	0.242	0.491	WH	0.276	0.242	0.482	WH	0.257	0.242	0.501
<i>Eopelobates deani</i>	J	0.529	0.433	0.037	J	0.535	0.425	0.040	J	0.522	0.443	0.035
<i>Eopelobates anthracinus</i>	Sw	0.165	0.425	0.410	Sw	0.168	0.419	0.412	Sw	0.160	0.431	0.409
<i>Eopelobates bayeri</i>	J	0.646	0.189	0.165	J	0.644	0.188	0.168	J	0.648	0.190	0.162
<i>Indobatrachus pusillus</i>	WH	0.369	0.200	0.431	WH	0.366	0.206	0.429	WH	0.372	0.193	0.434
<i>Cratia gracilis</i>	Sw	0.168	0.813	0.019	Sw	0.175	0.804	0.021	Sw	0.160	0.824	0.017
<i>Eurycephalella alcinae</i>	J	0.884	0.018	0.098	J	0.879	0.019	0.101	J	0.890	0.016	0.094
<i>Calypsocephalella canqueli</i>	WH	0.096	0.087	0.817	WH	0.101	0.091	0.808	WH	0.091	0.082	0.827
<i>Arariphrynus placidoi</i>	J	0.835	0.163	0.002	J	0.835	0.163	0.002	J	0.835	0.164	0.001
<i>Estesiella boliviensis</i>	Sw	0.086	0.495	0.419	Sw	0.088	0.497	0.416	Sw	0.085	0.493	0.423
<i>Liaobatrachus grabau</i>	J	0.460	0.199	0.341	J	0.451	0.209	0.340	J	0.470	0.188	0.342
<i>Liaobatrachus zhaoi</i>	Sw	0.083	0.716	0.200	Sw	0.085	0.713	0.202	Sw	0.082	0.719	0.199

<i>Liaobatrachus beiopiaoensis</i>	Sw	0.073	0.617	0.310		Sw	0.074	0.620	0.306		Sw	0.072	0.613	0.316
<i>Liaobatrachus macilentus</i>	Sw	0.033	0.924	0.044		Sw	0.034	0.920	0.046		Sw	0.031	0.928	0.041

TABLE S6. Prior probabilities used in pFDA.

	P(J)	P(Sw)	P(WH)
<i>Total dataset</i>	0.358	0.128	0.514
<i>Reduced dataset</i>	0.357	0.134	0.51

TABLE S7. Resulting loadings of pFDA under optimal lambdas.

	Total dataset		Reduced dataset	
	[1]	[2]	[1]	[2]
<i>Humerus</i>	-	-	832.526	952.450
	478.999	644.594	8	3
<i>Radioulna</i>	-	-	825.027	946.767
	496.919	658.326	7	8
<i>Femur</i>	-	-	824.627	933.415
	491.043	670.585	4	8
<i>Tibiofibula</i>	-	-	847.979	936.711
	462.438	667.542	8	
<i>Proximal</i>	-	-	838.619	942.566
<i>Tarsals</i>	482.516	663.901	8	3
<i>Metacarpal arch</i>	-	-		
	474.996	679.721		
<i>Metatarsal arch</i>	-	-		
	501.544	667.961		

TABLE S8. Classification of extant species by pFDA using the total dataset and the optimal lambda value + 0.02 (A-C), and -0.02 (D-F). *A. and D.:* Raw number of species. *B. and E.:* Diagonal: % of species with the LM of the column correctly classified as such; Off-Diagonal: % of species with the LM of the column misclassified under the LM of the row. *C. and F.:* Diagonal: % of species classified under the LM of the row that actually have this LM; Off-Diagonal: % of species misclassified under the LM of the row that actually have the LM of the column. Abbreviations: J, jumping; LM, locomotor mode; Sw, swimming; WH, walking-hopping.

A.		True LM			D.		True LM		
Predicted LM	<i>J</i>	<i>Sw</i>	<i>WH</i>	Predicted LM	<i>J</i>	<i>Sw</i>	<i>WH</i>		
<i>J</i>	145	6	18	<i>J</i>	146	7	19		
<i>Sw</i>	3	18	9	<i>Sw</i>	3	17	9		
<i>WH</i>	13	4	189	<i>WH</i>	12	4	188		

B.		True LM			E.		True LM		
Predicted LM	<i>J</i>	<i>Sw</i>	<i>WH</i>	Predicted LM	<i>J</i>	<i>Sw</i>	<i>WH</i>		
<i>J</i>	90.06	21.43	8.33	<i>J</i>	90.68	25.00	8.80		
<i>Sw</i>	1.86	64.29	4.17	<i>Sw</i>	1.86	60.71	4.17		
<i>WH</i>	8.07	14.29	87.50	<i>WH</i>	7.45	14.29	87.04		

C.		True LM			F.		True LM		
Predicted LM	<i>J</i>	<i>Sw</i>	<i>WH</i>	Predicted LM	<i>J</i>	<i>Sw</i>	<i>WH</i>		
<i>J</i>	85.80	3.55	10.65	<i>J</i>	84.88	4.07	11.05		
<i>Sw</i>	10.00	60.00	30.00	<i>Sw</i>	10.34	58.62	31.03		
<i>WH</i>	6.31	1.94	91.75	<i>WH</i>	5.88	1.96	92.16		

TABLE S9. Classification of extant species by pFDA using the reduced dataset and the optimal lambda value (A-C), the optimal + 0.02 (D-F), and -0.02 (G-I). *A., D., and G.:* Raw number of species. *A., E., and H.:* Diagonal: % of species with the LM of the column correctly classified as such; Off-Diagonal: % of species with the LM of the column misclassified under the LM of the row. *C., F., and I.:* Diagonal: % of species classified under the LM of the row that actually have this LM; Off-Diagonal: % of species misclassified under the LM of the row that actually have the LM of the column. Abbreviations: J, jumping; LM, locomotor mode; Sw, swimming; WH, walking-hopping.

A.				D.				G.						
		True LM					True LM					True LM		
Predicted LM	<i>J</i>	<i>Sw</i>	<i>WH</i>	Predicted LM	<i>J</i>	<i>Sw</i>	<i>WH</i>	Predicted LM	<i>J</i>	<i>Sw</i>	<i>WH</i>			
<i>J</i>	134	16	24	<i>J</i>	131	16	23	<i>J</i>	137	16	24			
<i>Sw</i>	15	9	10	<i>Sw</i>	15	9	9	<i>Sw</i>	14	9	10			
<i>WH</i>	14	4	185	<i>WH</i>	17	4	187	<i>WH</i>	12	4	185			

B.				E.				H.						
		True LM					True LM					True LM		
Predicted LM	<i>J</i>	<i>Sw</i>	<i>WH</i>	Predicted LM	<i>J</i>	<i>Sw</i>	<i>WH</i>	Predicted LM	<i>J</i>	<i>Sw</i>	<i>WH</i>			
<i>J</i>	82.2	55.1	10.9	<i>J</i>	80.3	55.1	10.5	<i>J</i>	84.0	55.1	10.9			
	1	7	6		7	7	0		5	7	6			
<i>Sw</i>	9.20	31.0	4.57	<i>Sw</i>	9.20	31.0	4.11	<i>Sw</i>	8.59	31.0	4.57			
		13.7	84.4		10.4	13.7	85.3			13.7	84.4			
<i>WH</i>	8.59	9	7	<i>WH</i>	3	9	9	<i>WH</i>	7.36	9	7			

C.				F.				I.						
		True LM					True LM					True LM		
Predicted LM	<i>J</i>	<i>Sw</i>	<i>WH</i>	Predicted LM	<i>J</i>	<i>Sw</i>	<i>WH</i>	Predicted LM	<i>J</i>	<i>Sw</i>	<i>WH</i>			
<i>J</i>	77.0	13.7	9	<i>J</i>	77.0	13.5	3	<i>J</i>	77.4	13.5	6			
	1	9.20	29.4		6	9.41	27.2		0	9.04	30.3			
<i>Sw</i>	44.1	26.4	1	<i>Sw</i>	45.4	27.2	7	<i>Sw</i>	42.4	27.2	0			
	2	7	91.1		5	7	89.9		2	7	92.0			
<i>WH</i>	6.90	1.97	3	<i>WH</i>	8.17	1.92	0	<i>WH</i>	5.97	1.99	4			